

Deconstructing the Evolutionary Negative Narrative: Exploring the Hidden Positive Realities of the World

The number of errors we can make when describing the world is incredible. This is because, in general, we tend to be biased towards negative aspects, even though the world today is the best it has ever been. Most people, including those who are relatively well-educated, often think that the world is more violent than in the past. Another bias arises from the concept of well-being. For example, the world tends to believe that "underdeveloped countries" are in worse conditions than they actually are. However, statistics show that by the year 2000, about one-third of humanity lived in extreme poverty, whereas today, this condition affects less than 10% of the global population. In other words, the world is progressing towards greater well-being. So, how can we be so negative? No, it's not a matter of interpretation or desire. These are simply facts that are curiously available to everyone but often overlooked.

When we ask people about life expectancy, female education, or even the percentage of people vaccinated against certain diseases, most people respond incorrectly... very incorrectly. In fact, our knowledge is even worse than that of a chimpanzee choosing random answers.

This book reveals the cause of these errors. It is primarily due to our minds. From an evolutionary perspective, our brains are not prepared to understand a complex and ever-changing world. Therefore, we have had to adapt to recognize a few elements of our environment and quickly draw conclusions that increase our chances of survival. However, this quickness does not guarantee accuracy or correctness; it simply means that we generate conclusions that are circumstantially useful, nothing more. Essentially, it is an evolutionary mechanism that tends to conclude that unexpected things are negative for us because our ancestors who considered the unexpected as positive eventually died. In other words, those who survived were extremely cautious. Today, we pay more attention to information that aligns with our more dramatic instincts.

This evolutionary mechanism, which biases us toward quickly perceiving negative events, is associated with other effects. For example, having a narrative (regardless of whether it is positive or negative) about something will always serve as a filter of reality that protects us from the noise of the world. Therefore, it is not reality itself. This makes it almost impossible to draw conclusions about the causes of things because everything that happens in the world affects everything else that will happen, not just what I arbitrarily choose. It is impossible to isolate effects. This is particularly evident in politics, where one group attributes the causes of a society's problems to a particular idea simply because it seems convincing within a simplified context (and by definition, incorrect or imprecise). This type of thinking has led to the deaths of millions of people due to anchoring to this thinking error: my simplified model of the world (which doesn't exist) doesn't match yours (which also doesn't exist).

The problem is that we don't think this way. We are not aware that what we think are nothing more than inaccurate representations of the world. We are also not aware that we are terrible at statistics and don't understand how to apply it to describe the world. This bias leads to a positive feedback loop with respect to the news that appears in the media. In other words, the media takes advantage

of our intrinsic demand to map the world's dangers, making us believe that the world is worse than it actually is. In fact, people with similar incomes are more similar to each other than we imagine. This means that lifestyles are more alike, so cultures or religions are not as distinct divisions today as the media might make us think.

This book is significant because it offers a ray of hope in the face of the common state of the world. It's heartening to know that the world we learned about 20 years ago bears little resemblance to the world today, and the current world will be different in almost every aspect from the world 20 years into the future. Poverty is decreasing, and opportunities are increasing. Apparently, the world is moving toward a society where everyone tends to have a better quality of life, regardless of their region, culture, or worldview. That's why it's recommended that we be curious about things, relearn (hopefully, everyone), and realize that the news is a poor source for understanding the world. It isolates us, creates stereotypes, and anchors us to an outdated view of an invisible division: "us vs. them." It can even create the illusion that dangers are external and that we are "superior" to others. Hans Rosling advises us to control the instincts that cause stress in a world portrayed in an overly dramatic manner. He urges us to focus on specific problems to solve them.

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References

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